

Workshop on Research Objects at IEEE eScience Conference

Implementing a Flexible Infrastructure for a Digital Object Based Data Management

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Data Intensive science, a Fourth Dimension of Science as introduced by J. Gray [1] is a fact in many large institutions, however, participation is mainly limited to data scientists in those institutions, i.e. many scientists are excluded, and many relevant data driven scientific questions can simply not be taken up, since the costs are too high. Similarly we are far away from a flourishing data economy where many companies can participate, in particular innovative small enterprises and start-ups. There are a number of different reasons for this situation including uncertainties with respect to legal issues. Here, we want to address an issue which is conceptual as well as technical.

It is known from various studies that our data work suffers from large inefficiencies: about 80% of a data scientist's time in science and industry is wasted with data wrangling mainly due to a lack of interoperability at all levels and bad data quality [2]. In addition to the semantic interoperability problems which are inherent to big data science when data from different sources need to be integrated, it is the lack of interoperability and machine actionability in data organisation¹ which creates so much overhead and which prevents increased automation which is needed for scalability. Data, in our sense, includes not only the primary content stored as bit-sequences in various repositories, but also descriptive metadata, provenance metadata, rights metadata, license metadata, transaction metadata, fingerprint information, and so on, all being necessary for meaningful processing and long-term management of the content. Currently, these entities are scattered over different locations and in different environments and there is no simple widely agreed mechanism to get seamless access to them. For distributed scenarios there is no specification yet that indicates, for example, where you can find the descriptive or rights metadata once you have found interesting bit-sequences.

In many domains the challenges go beyond the technical dimension of data organisation. The challenge is to have scientifically meaningful entities in the digital data domain organised such that the relevant relationships for such meaningful entities are represented in a stable way, completely independent of any technological developments. In science we must understand that we are building structures that need to last a very long time in order to organise an utterly dynamic universe of data. Ordering this domain will cost an enormous amount of effort and funding, and will require fundamental solutions accepted globally and across sciences.

Based on these convictions and some specification work in initiatives such as the Research Data Alliance [3] a group of institutions of different types (research infrastructures, data and compute centres, global service providers) represented by key data scientists decided to collaborate on the development of a scalable and flexible infrastructure for a data management regime based on Digital Objects. The group is currently named C2CAMP [4].

¹ In a phase where we speak about "data lakes" data comes along based on very different data models which typically define structures and relations of entities in a closed descriptive domain such as a model of reality in an entity-relationship model (relational database).

Digital Objects were introduced by Kahn and Wilensky in 1995 [5] after they recognised that the basic layer of Internet where meaningless messages are being exchanged between Internet devices needs to be extended to a layer of meaningful objects to be exchanged and processed. With FTP a first application for exchanging files was developed on top of the basic TCP/IP Internet protocols. Later the World Wide Web was defined to exchange and access web-information using the HTTP protocol. URLs were used to point to locations of entities and the web's openness motivated many people and companies to develop utterly successful solutions for various purposes. However, these approaches tackle sub-domains in the management of digital data and cannot be seen as generic solutions for the challenges described above and now being put to the test by the coming developments with the billions of smart devices all creating continuous data streams.

RDA's Data Fabric & Terminology group defined Digital Objects (DO) as having a bit sequence stored in repositories, being references by a unique, persistent and globally resolvable identifier (PID) and being described by different types of metadata [6]. The group also argued that we will need to make sure that everyone can rely on the existence of system of globally resolvable and stable PIDs and that it makes sense to use PIDs to connect all kinds of binding information that relate DOs to their constituent entities. In RDA's Data Fabric group we realised the key role of PIDs and more specification work was started such as to define ways to register kernel attributes used in the PID record to create interoperability [7]. ITU accepted the standard X.1255 [8] for interoperability between identifier systems. Also the relevance of "types" associated with DOs and stored in the PID record became obvious as a major step towards automation. The specifications of RDA's Data Type Registry group [9] allows linking types of DOs with procedures to be executed, making DOs not only passive entities, but first class citizens in the increasingly complex digital data domain.

The C2CAMP collaboration agreed to not only pursue specification/recommendation work, but to implement a DO based infrastructure where different essential components coming from RDA and other initiatives and technology provider will be integrated to demonstrate the usefulness of a DO centric data domain. Scientific disciplines are eager to use the conceptual value of the DO approach and to implement application scenarios where DOs offer unique possibilities. Large data and compute centres see the need to add a DO based data management dimension to their work to give efficient support to their customers. Global service providers see the possibility to develop layered services on top of their PID services for the benefit of science.

C2CAMP continues to collaborate with RDA to develop specifications of infrastructure components and interfaces on a broad basis, to act as a GO FAIR [10] implementation network to interact with implementers tackling other areas of relevance, to interact with other global initiatives that are working on similar aspects such as, for example, Research Objects [11]. In focus for the coming months is an interaction in particular with DONA [12] to work on a Digital Object Interface Protocol which will be crucial for realising a functioning DO centric data infrastructure.

The presentation will include the aspects which are indicated in this description and discuss the potential value of DOs as foundational data models across different scientific communities of practice.

[1] Tony Hey, Stewart Tansley, Kristin Tolle: The Fourth Paradigm: Data-Intensive Scientific Discovery, <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/publication/fourth-paradigm-data-intensive-scientific-discovery/>

[2] Peter Wittenburg, George Strawn: Common Patterns in Revolutionary Infrastructures and Data, <http://doi.org/10.23728/b2share.4e8ac36c0dd343da81fd9e83e72805a0>

[3] Research Data Alliance: <http://rd-alliance.org>

[4] Ari asmi et. al., Interlinking Digital Repositories: Digital Objects as Foundational Entities in the Global Data World, <http://doi.org/10.23728/b2share.e16da3527a314fca1f5984d0b00ca31>

- [5] Kahn, Robert E., Robert Wilensky, "A Framework for Distributed Digital Object Services". *International Journal on Digital Libraries*, (2006) 6(2): 115-123. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00799-005-0128-x>. Reproduced by the International DOI Foundation with permission of the publisher [here](#). (First published by the authors May 13, 1995, "A Framework for Distributed Digital Object Services", <http://hdl.handle.net/4263537/5001>).
- [6] RDA Data Foundation & Terminology: DFT Core Terms and Model, <http://hdl.handle.net/11304/5d760a3e-991d-11e5-9bb4-2b0aad496318>
- [7] RDA Data Fabric IG: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/data-fabric-ig.html>
- [8] ITU X.1255: Framework for discovery of identity management information, <https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-X.1255-201309-I>
- [9] RDA's Data Type Registry: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/data-type-registries-wg/post/data-type-registry-first-prototype.html>
- [10] <https://www.go-fair.org/>
- [11] <http://www.researchobject.org/>
- [12] <https://www.dona.net/>